

LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK FAIRY TALES

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Abstract: *This article explains the linguo-cultural, comparative, cognitive and practical linguo-cultural issues specific to the fairy tale genre of English and Uzbek folklore. Also, the importance of the linguistic approach to language analysis is emphasized.*

Key words: *Linguistic culture, cultural, codes, folklore, literary means, revitalization.*

A fairy tale is one of the main genres of folk oral poetic creation, it is an epic artistic work of a magical adventure and domestic character based on texture and fiction, that is, it is mainly created in the form of prose. A fairy tale is a compact story that includes folkloric features such as fairies, goblins, princes and princesses. Fairy tales are a subclass of folk art. The oldest tales were told orally and passed down from generation to generation until they were written down. A closer examination of these stories reveals that there are several, or even more than 10, versions of the same tale. Each fairy tale has its own way of telling and cultural elements. This factor often depends on the place and time of the incident. Today, various authors still enjoy inventing and writing new versions of fairy tales (Hallett & Karasek, 2009; Tiberghien 2007).

The desire to understand the phenomenon of the linguocultural content of language and culture as one of the forms of existence of the surrounding linguistic factor causes the formation and development of the linguocultural direction. Its linguistic and cultural space has its own interpretation, and it is considered the torus

of not only national, but also world culture. It should be noted that the main subject of cultural linguistics can include several areas:

1. cognitive-semiological cultural linguistics aimed at studying the characteristics of language units from the point of view of determining emotional results;
2. historical linguoculturology, which broadly analyzes national and world linguocultures;
3. historical and typological cultural linguistics studying the stages of development of linguocultures;
4. comparative cultural linguistics aimed at solving pragma
5. cognitive cultural linguistics, which analyzes the units of culture and linguistic culture included in the main cognitive base;
6. cultural linguistics of a particular social group, ethnos, sub-ethnos, aimed at understanding a certain linguocultural situation or a certain cultural period.

The educational role of fairy tales is incomparable. Because they create an opportunity for children to grow up in a healthy environment and start them on the right path. At this point, it is important to mention the opinions expressed by V. G. Gusev about fairy tales. In his opinion, "In society, in general, the vices of human nature, when they are not reflected in real life, find their solution in fairy tales in a fantastic way. "Scholars express their different views on linguistic and cultural issues. For example, according to the Russian linguist Fedosov, "... Linguistics (language) ... expresses cultural concepts. Thus, cultural studies precedes linguistics." To name and express one concept, you need to start directly from the adapted part (Fedosov, 2015). Research in science begins with the components of national and cultural vocabulary (Maslova, 2001, 2010). "The analysis of examples of the English language shows that all the differences of modern speech between English and Russian cultures, the conceptualization strategy in this area are characterized by similarities rather than differences" (Kurguzenkova, 2016: 97).⁶

Linguistic codes, according to Maslova, "form existence and occupy a central place in the national cultural space. At the same time, it is a means of systematizing cultural knowledge "(Maslova, 2016: 33). The connection with folklore is especially important when it comes to a literary tale genetically derived from a folk tale. Folklore is an oral folk creation that reflects the artistic collective creative activity of the people, embodies the people's ideas about life, as well as views and ideals; created by people and available in different genres. It is the linguocultural approach that makes it possible to interpret the text as a cultural and linguistic phenomenon, in which the specific features of the national culture of the people who created it are most clearly revealed. Various artistic tools are used in fairy tales to interest the reader, develop their imagination and attract them to themselves. These resources can be named differently: tools, elements, resources, etc

Literary devices are specific language techniques that writers use to create text that is usually clear, interesting, and memorable. Words or parts of words can be clustered or placed side by side to achieve specific types of effects when we hear them. Many words can have several meanings at the same time, and thus artistic devices can be created. In fact, the study of figurative language has a long history. Ancient philosophers such as Aristotle were among the first to theorize the use and function of figurative language and the related field. Aristotle emphasized that figurative language is not just a decoration, but a vital reflection of the real state of people by comparing them to things we are already familiar with.

In English literature, there is also an artistic tool of imagery (imagery), and Kinesthetic imagery modality is determined by the reflection of how to perform an action, expressed through aspects such as force and movement. For example:

"The young man gave a thousand coins, took the rooster and threw it on the field.

"The bald rooster is clucking, laughing, looking at his opponent on the field every now and then, as if a grain has fallen from the ground."

Or:

"The jeweler gave the watch and chain. The bird took it in one foot, the shoes in the other, and, after repeating the song, flew away to where three millers were picking a millstone. The bird perched on a tree and sang..."

Thus, fairy tales can reflect specific cultural and stylistic features. These can be seen in the example of Uzbek and English fairy tales.

References:

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2. Maslova V.A. *Linguoculturology: textbook*. 4th ed. M., 2010.